

The Effect of Cognitive Behavioral Therapy on Self-Control, Mental Health and Mindfulness of Women Suffering from Domestic Violence

Parisa Sabzevari¹, Ahmad Torabi^{*2}, Horrieh Abbasmofrad³, Leila Asgari Doost⁴, Zahra Taher Nasab Amiri⁵, Elham Ariya Faraz⁶, Mehri Azandariani⁷

1. PhD in Counseling , Department of Educational Sciences , Mashhad Branch, Islamic Azad University , Mashhad, Iran

2. Master of clinical psychology, Department of psychology, Sari Branch , Islamic Azad University, Sari, Iran (corresponding Author) ahmadtorabi66@gmail.com

3. PhD student in health psychology, Islamic Azad University, Karaj Branch, Karaj, Iran

4. Master of General psychology, Department of psychology, Mahallat Branch, Islamic Azad University, Mahallat, Iran

5. Master of General psychology, Department of psychology, South Tehran Branch, Islamic Azad University, South Tehran, Iran

6. Master of clinical psychology, Department of psychology, Ayatollah Amoli Branch, Islamic Azad University, Amol, Iran

7. PhD in Counseling , Department of Educational Sciences , Mashhad Branch, Islamic Azad University , Mashhad, Iran

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Abstract :

The aim of this research was the effect of cognitive behavioral therapy on self-control, mental health and mindfulness of women suffering from domestic violence. The research was semi-experimental with a pre-test and post-test design and with a control group. The statistical population included all married women suffering from domestic violence who referred to Andisheh Sabz Center of Qom in

1401, 30 people were selected by available sampling method and assigned in two equal groups of 15 people. In addition to demographic information checklist, data collection was done with self-control questionnaire, mental health questionnaire and mindfulness questionnaire. For the subjects of the experimental groups, 12 sessions, one 1-hour session per week. In addition to descriptive statistics, data analysis was performed with repeated measures analysis of variance. The results showed that in the post-test stage, there is a significant difference between the total score of self-control and its dimensions in the two groups ($P<0.05$). Also, the results showed that in the post-test stage, there is a significant difference between the mental health score and its dimensions in people participating in intervention programs and control people ($P<0.05$). Also, the results showed that in the post-test stage, there is a significant difference between the mindfulness score and its dimensions in people participating in intervention programs and control people ($P<0.05$).

Keywords: cognitive behavioral therapy, self-control, mental health, mindfulness, family violence

Introduction

Family is the first social organization in which a person lives, and it is basically a center of help, relief, and healing, and it should decrease the mental pressure on its members and pave the way for their growth and prosperity (Mollamohamadi, 2018). One of the mental pressures that is very common today and endangers the foundations of families is domestic violence (Kumar, 2020). Violence towards spouse is one of the major problems of many countries including Iran, which brings many negative cultural, physical, and mental consequences for the victims. A culture's view of family, women and violence, social structure and laws governing a society, economic status, and peoples' general opinions and beliefs are among the issues that can help to explain domestic violence in any society on a macro level (Megan et al., 2020). Domestic violence is the most common form of violence with the highest probability of repetition and the least report to the police and the most social, psychological, and economic complications, which can seriously damage the foundations of a family and lead to its collapse (Yacoubi et al., 2016). Domestic violence refers to the aggressive and domineering behavior of a family member against another member or members of the same family (Ertan et al., 2020). Given that domestic violence is one of the common issues that has attracted the attention of many researchers across the world today, it is still considered a common social harm (Isvand and Pirouzmand, 2019). Family violence is one of the most important social harms that continue to exist in society despite

intellectual and cultural progresses. Among the various types of domestic violence, women's violence against men has received less attention (Mittal & Singth, 2020). Domestic violence is strongly effective on decreasing psychological well-being (Perin, 2018), marital satisfaction (Walter et al., 2016), marital intimacy (Karen et al., 2017), and quality of married life of couples (Shah Hosseini et al., 2018), and quality of parent-child relationship (Pourmand et al., 2016).

In order to increase the compatibility of couples and decrease marital distress in their married life and improve the mental health of couples and, as a result, improve family functioning, there are various therapeutic approaches, including cognitive-behavioral therapies (CBT) (McCrary et al., 2016). This therapy is an overarching term for a general set of therapies (Twohig, 2012). Cognitive-behavioral couple therapy (CBCT) is the combination of cognitive and behavioral factors in the treatment of couples with marital problems. The cognitive foundations of cognitive-behavioral couple therapy emphasize mutual recognition of couples and consider recognition as an integral part of the process of couples' change. Finally, the philosophical basis of this perception is that change in behavior alone is not enough to correct dysfunctional interactions, but rather the way of thinking of people in incompatible behavioral patterns and relationships should be emphasized (Lv et al., 2021). In a study, Siddique, Chung, Brown & Miranda (2012) compared the effectiveness of cognitive-behavioral couple therapy and medication therapy on depression and mental health of married women. The results indicated that cognitive-behavioral couple therapy was more effective in decreasing the symptoms of depression and improving their mental health. Therefore, this method of therapy helps clients to achieve a more valuable and more satisfying life through psychological flexibility (Forman and Butryn, 2015). One of the variables that appears to be affected by cognitive behavioral therapy is self-control. Self-control expresses the conformity of one's behavioral characteristics to the existing conditions and situation (Avazpour and Touzande, 2021) and it means how flexible or stable a person is in their situation (Moser et al., 2020). People who can prioritize realistic goals and balance emotions and reason when making decisions are self-controlled (Moayyeri, 2020). People who lack self-control are vulnerable to tempting and seductive moments (Demirtaş, 2020). Thus, they suffer from panic and stress and lose their calm in sensitive situations such as the occurrence of dangerous diseases, (Yang et al., 2021). People in corona conditions should have higher self-control in order to overcome their very high stress (Schnell & Krampe, 2020). Another variable that appears to be affected by cognitive behavioral therapy is mental health.

On the other hand, in recent years, the approach of positive psychology has a special opinion on the positive dimensions of human existence, that positive thoughts and emotions have a unique effect on the mental and physical health of a person. In this approach, the ultimate goal is to identify the constructs and methods that contribute to human well-being, happiness, and growth. Therefore, the factors that cause a person to adapt more and more to the needs and threats of life are the most fundamental constructs under the research of this approach (Sacco et al., 2021). Mental health is one of the factors that can be studied for its effect and relationship with the performance of marital relationships. In recent years, the pathological approach to the study of human health has been criticized. Contrary to this view that defines health as the absence of disease, the new approach emphasizes "being good" instead of "being bad or sick" (Din Mohammadi et al., 2021). From this point of view, the absence of symptoms of mental illnesses is not an indicator of health, but adaptability, happiness, self-confidence and positive characteristics of this kind indicate health, and the main goal of a person in life is to flourish their capabilities (Roslan et al., 2017). The mental health of couples leads to expanding the capabilities of couples and their growth, strengthening the communication skills of couples (Javadi Vala et al., 2021), resolving conflicts between couples (Tasew et al., 2021), expanding the personal goals of couples and families (Allahvardipour et al., 2021), and increasing intimacy between couples (Kataoka et al., 2018). One of the variables that appears to be affected by cognitive behavioral therapy is mindfulness.

Mindfulness is defined as awareness that arises from paying attention on purpose, in the present moment, and nonjudgmentally (Simon et al., 2018). Mindfulness includes a receptive and judgment-free awareness of what is happening now. Conscious people perceive internal and external realities freely and without distortion and have a great ability to face a wide range of pleasant or unpleasant thoughts, emotions, and experiences (Zarnaghash et al., 2015). Of course, mindfulness is not just for decreasing suffering, but it emphasizes the capacity of mindfulness for individual growth, compassion, and what causes individual and interpersonal growth. The effect of mindfulness is not only related to illness. Mindfulness of positive and negative emotions activates different mental mechanisms that affect mental health (Donnell et al., 2020).

The highest rate of violence is among women aged 25 to 35 years, proportionally, as the age increases, the level of violence decreases. Approximately 70% of the women who were subjected to violence had an educational level of diploma or lower than diploma, which is the highest value in the table. The

lowest level of violence is also among women who have a postgraduate education or higher (Bozorgi and Khodadadi, 2020). Also, the high prevalence of domestic violence in women can lead to suicide (Isvand and Pirouzmand, 2019), marital infidelity (Lisman & Holman, 2021), chronic pain syndrome, depression, and on the other hand, it causes drug abuse and sexually transmitted diseases, and various family and social problems (Bolhari et al., 2017). Domestic violence accounts for approximately 5 and 19% of the total burden of diseases in women aged 15 to 44 in developing and developed countries, respectively (Rosoulilian et al., 2015). Families in which there is a lot of violence raise opinionated and abnormal children with no self-confidence, and the efficiency of parents is also at a low level. Moreover, these people gradually become isolated and show weakness in social relations (Ahmadi et al., 2019).

Therefore, in the present research, the question to be addressed is what effect does cognitive behavioral therapy have on self-control, mental health, and mindfulness of women suffering from domestic violence?

Shabahang et al. (2021) in research entitled the effectiveness of online cognitive-behavioral intervention on health anxiety, anxiety sensitivity, and somatosensory amplification in healthy people with high levels of anxiety associated with covid-19 reached the conclusion that cognitive-behavioral intervention leads to a reduction of health anxiety, anxiety sensitivity, and somatosensory amplification, and reduction of violence of the participants in the experimental group. Zheng et al. (2021) in research entitled the effectiveness of cognitive behavioral therapy on the mood and quality of life of patients reached the conclusion that cognitive behavioral therapy had a positive and significant effect on reducing the aggression and violence of patients. Sadrzadeh et al. (2019) in research entitled investigating the causes of domestic violence in pregnant women referring to Mashhad's trauma centers concluded that the most important causes of domestic violence from the point of view of pregnant women were husband's unemployment and economic problems, previous history of hospital admission due to domestic violence and addiction of spouse. 16 patients left the hospital with personal consent and 30 patients were hospitalized. The number of cases of personal consent was significantly higher in patients affected by domestic violence than other traumas. Among the most important underlying causes of domestic violence in the current study, we can mention the history of violence in the individual or family, as well as unemployment and economic problems. Perrin (2018) in research entitled domestic violence and psychological well-being of couples concluded that domestic violence of couples has the

ability to predict the psychological well-being of couples. Karen (2017) in research entitled the effect of domestic violence on marital intimacy and physical/psychological well-being concluded that there is a significant relationship between marital intimacy and domestic violence and that there is also a significant relationship between physical/psychological well-being and domestic violence. Walter (2016) in research entitled predicting psychological well-being and marital satisfaction based on domestic violence concluded that domestic violence has a positive effect on psychological well-being and that marital satisfaction has a positive effect on psychological well-being. Seddiqi (2019) in her research entitled evaluation of the effect of group cognitive behavioral therapy on the mental health of working women affected by domestic violence reached the conclusion that group cognitive behavioral therapy has an effect on improving mental health, decreasing anxiety and sleep disorders, improving social functioning, reducing depression and reducing physical symptoms of working women affected by domestic violence.

Methodology

This research is semi-experimental and applied that was conducted with a pre-test-post-test design with a control group, and after determining and randomly placing the experimental and control groups (1 experimental group and 1 control group), cognitive-behavioral couple therapy was applied to the experimental group in the form of 12 sessions, each session lasting 1 hour (60 minutes), and a week after the completion of the therapy sessions, the experimental and control groups were subjected to a post-test. The statistical population of this research included all the women admitted to Andisheh Sabz Center with the subject of filing a case of domestic violence in 2022 who referred to this center to receive counseling and psychotherapy services. Simple random sampling method was used in this study. Thus, 30 samples were randomly selected from the clients. The inclusion criteria were: being a woman, being married for at least 5 years, not taking any psychotherapeutic drugs, not attending any other psychotherapeutic course, and obtaining a high score in Haj Yahya's domestic violence questionnaire and individual consent in participating in psychotherapeutic courses. Finally, they were randomly assigned to two equal groups of 15 people. The sample size was calculated by the mean comparison formula with a confidence coefficient of 95% and a test power of 80%. The criteria for exclusion from the research included the individual's lack of consent and willingness, the individual's suffering from one of the chronic (medical-psychiatric) problems and the use of certain medications, not filling the questionnaires completely, being absent in the intervention sessions for more than two

sessions, participating in therapy sessions similar to the present study at the same time or 6 months ago and the subject's lack of willingness and consent.

The implementation method is such that first the necessary coordination was made with the officials of Andisheh Sabz Center by explaining the purpose of the research, the method of its implementation, compliance with ethical considerations and the method of publishing the results in the city. Then, we went to the center and the intended sample was determined after 1 month. Then, the pre-test was conducted in this center during two sessions. The sessions were conducted separately and independently for each group according to approved health protocols. Then, 10 days after the completion of the intervention sessions, the post-test stage was conducted for all sample subjects.

The hypotheses followed in the present research are as follows:

- Cognitive behavioral therapies affect the self-control of women suffering from domestic violence.
- Cognitive behavioral therapies affect the mental health of women suffering from domestic violence.
- Cognitive behavioral therapies affect the mindfulness of women suffering from domestic violence.

Tools

A) Domestic violence questionnaire (Haj Yahya, 1998)

The data collection tool in the present research is Haj Yahya's domestic violence questionnaire (1998). It has 32 items based on 4 factors. The first factor, which includes articles 1 to 16, measures psychological violence, the second factor, which includes articles 17 to 27, measures physical violence, the third factor, which includes articles 28 to 30, measures sexual violence, and the fourth factor, which includes articles 31 and 32, measures economic violence. In the research of Amiri Shamili (2014), the validity of the questionnaire was calculated through face validity, so that the questionnaire measuring violence against women was translated by the researcher, and its face validity was confirmed based on the CVR and CVI indices (all values are high and close to one). In Amiri Shamili's research (2014), Cronbach's alpha coefficient was used to calculate reliability, and its value was 0.86.

B) Mental health questionnaire: GHQ

The 28-question general health questionnaire was presented by Goldberg and Hillier (1979) and has 4 subscales and each scale has 7 questions. The mentioned scales are:

1. Scale of physical symptoms
2. Scale of anxiety symptoms and sleep disorder
3. Scale of social functioning
4. Scale of depression symptoms

Out of the 28 items in the questionnaire, items 1 to 7 are related to the scale of physical symptoms. Items 8 to 14 examine the symptoms of anxiety and sleep disorder, and items 15 to 21 are related to the evaluation of symptoms of social functioning, and finally items 22 to 28 measure the symptoms of depression. To sum up the scores, A is given zero, B is given 1, C is given 2, and D is given 3. In each scale, a score of 6 or above and a total score of 22 or above indicates morbid symptoms. Alian and Ghasemi (2016) have confirmed the validity and reliability of this questionnaire in their research.

C) Self-control questionnaire

This questionnaire has been provided by Tanji (1999). Tanji's self-control questionnaire has 13 questions and its purpose is to measure the level of people's control over themselves. Also, this questionnaire is one-dimensional. The response range was of the Likert type (very high=5, high=4, occasionally=3, rarely=2, never=1). However, this method of scoring has been reversed in questions 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 9, 10, 12, and 13. In order to obtain the total score of the questionnaire, add up the total scores of all the questions together. The maximum score for Tanji's self-control questionnaire is 65 and the minimum is 13. A higher score indicates a higher self-control and vice versa. Validity and reliability of Tanji's self-control questionnaire have been calculated and confirmed in Mousavi Moghadam et al.'s research (2014). In the research of Tanji et al. (2004), the validity of this scale has been confirmed by evaluating its correlation with the scales of academic achievement, adaptability, positive relationships, and interpersonal skills. Also, its reliability has been obtained at 0.83 and 0.85 on two statistical samples using Cronbach's alpha test.

D) Mindfulness

MAAS mindfulness questionnaire

This questionnaire was designed by Brown and Ryan (2003) to measure mindfulness, which has 15 items and the items are in cognitive, emotional, interpersonal, physical, and other general areas. It is scored on a six-point Likert scale. This scale provides an overall score for mindfulness that ranges from 15 to 90, with a higher score indicating greater mindfulness. This scale was standardized in the student population in 2014 by Abdi and Ghabeli. The reliability of this scale has been reported as 0.76 and its validity has been confirmed.

D) Content of sessions

Table 1. Summary of cognitive-behavioral couple therapy sessions (CBT)

Session	Training content (purpose)	Method of intervention	Assignment
First	Communication	Getting familiar with the cognitive-behavioral model and intervention aims	-
Second	Behavioral skills	Role playing, knowing patterns of reinforcement and punishment, increasing positive behavioral exchange and decreasing negative exchange	Performing two positive behaviors and reducing one negative behavior, daily attention list
Third	Behavioral skills	Dependency contracts, role reversal	Agreement to exchange favorable behaviors
Fourth	Behavioral skills	Daring, behavioral testing and its practice	Applying behavioral testing
Fifth	Behavioral skills	Active listening, sender and receiver skills	Correcting communication skills
the sixth	Behavioral skills	Determining specific negative interactions, practicing effective communication	Practicing effective communication skills

the seventh	Cognitive factors	Down arrow, identifying automatic thoughts and emotions	Completing a daily recording of inefficient thoughts
Eighth	Cognitive factors	Recognizing schemas, cognitive processes	Discovering important relationship schemas
ninth	Cognitive factors	Explaining the spouse's behavior, recognizing cognitive errors	Correcting cognitive errors
Tenth	Cognitive factors	Documentation patterns, explaining unrealistic expectations	Practicing tell me what you like
Eleventh	Problem solving skills	Evaluation and practice of problem solving, activity planning	Practicing activity planning
Twelfth	Conflict resolution skills	Identifying and practicing conflict resolution methods	Resolving a specific conflict

(Source: Barron and Storch, 2021)

Findings

Descriptive findings related to the variables of the present research are given in Tables 2, 3, and 4:

Table 2. Mean and standard deviation of mental health and its dimensions separately sorted by group and stages of measurement

Variable	Group	Number	Pretest	Posttest
			M ± SD	M ± SD
Physical symptoms	CBCT	15	15.07±0.55	12.93±1.13
	Control	15	12.67±1.11	12.19±0.76
Anxiety symptoms	CBCT	15	15.10±1.19	11.45±2.65
	Control	15	12.16±1.73	11.88±1.14
Social function	CBCT	15	12.13±1.15	16.02±2.87

Depression symptoms	Control	15	11.00±0.27	10.55±0.15
	CBCT	15	14.51±2.89	11.19±6.65
	Control	15	12.83±3.11	12.62±2.05

The results of Table 3 show that the mean score of people in the cognitive behavioral therapy couple group in the variable of physical symptoms in the pretest stage is 15.07 (12.67) and 12.93 (12.19) in the posttest stage. The mean score of people in the cognitive-behavioral couple therapy group in the variable of anxiety symptoms is 15.10 (and 12.16) in the pretest stage and 11.45 (and 11.88) in the posttest stage. The mean score of people in the cognitive-behavioral couple therapy group in the variable of social function is 12.13 (and 11.00) in the pretest stage and 16.02 (and 10.55) in the posttest stage. The mean score of people in the cognitive-behavioral couple therapy group in the variable of depression symptoms is 14.51 (and 12.83) in the pretest stage and 11.19 (and 12.62) in the posttest stage. The mean score of the variables in the control group does not show a noticeable change from the pretest to the posttest stages.

Table 3. Mean and standard deviation of self-control and its dimensions separately sorted by group and stages of measurement

Variable	Group	Number	Pretest	Posttest
			M ± SD	M ± SD
Self-control	CBCT	15	30.45±0.68	46.70±1.09
	Control	15	30.98±1.42	30.34±0.97

The results of Table 3 show that the mean score of people in the cognitive behavioral therapy couple group in the variable of self-control is 30.45 (30.98) in the pretest stage and 46.70 (30.34) in the posttest stage. The mean score of the variables in the control group does not show a noticeable change from the pretest to the posttest stages.

Table 4. Mean and standard deviation of mindfulness and its dimensions separately sorted by group and stages of measurement

Variable	Group	Number	Pretest	Posttest
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			M ± SD	M ± SD
Mindfulness	CBCT	15	46.69±0.77	72.49±1.25
	Control	15	45.62±1.38	45.21±1.29

The results of Table 4 show that the mean score of people in the cognitive behavioral therapy group in the variable of mindfulness is 46.69 (45.62) in the pretest stage and 72.49 (45.21) in the posttest stage. The mean score of the variables in the control group does not show a noticeable change from the pretest to the posttest stages.

Table 5. Results of Shapiro-Wilk and Kolmogorov-Smirnov tests for the normality of distribution of scores

Dependent variables	Shapiro-Wilk test		Kolmogorov-Smirnov test	
	Statistic	Sig. level	Statistic	Sig. level
Self-control	0.061	0.223	0.116	0.364
Mental health	0.310	0.544	0.285	0.597
Mindfulness	0.187	0.399	0.139	0.443

One of the necessary assumptions for using parametric tests is normal distribution of scores of the sample group or groups in a population. This assumption is based on that it is assumed that the distribution of scores in the population is normal and if there is skewness or kurtosis in the sample groups, it is due to random sampling of people. The assumption of normality is rejected if the probability of randomness of the difference between the distribution of the sample groups and the normality of the scores in the population becomes less than 0.05.

Table 6. Results of Box's M test based on the homogeneity of the variance-covariance matrices

Dependent variables	Box's M test statistic	F test statistic	Sig. level
Self-control	2.624	1.342	0.260
Mental health	1.810	0.765	0.425
Mindfulness	4.766	0.701	0.249

Box's M test was also used to check the homogeneity of the variance-covariance matrix. According to the data in Table 6, the results of this test show that because the significance level obtained is greater than 0.05, the research data did not question the assumption of equality of variance-covariance matrices. Since the variance-covariance matrices have homogeneity, the variance test can be used in this research.

Table 7. Results of Levene's test on the assumption of homogeneity of error in variances

Dependent variables	F statistic	Sig. level
Self-control	0.686	0.488
Mental health	1.543	0.639
Mindfulness	1.674	0.512

Another assumption for using analysis of variance is equality of variance of groups. The assumption of equality of variances is based on that the variance of scores for two groups in the population is equal and that there is no statistically significant difference. In this research, Levene's test was used to check the assumption of equality of variances before carrying out the analysis of variance, the results of which are given in Table 7.

Table 8. Results of homogeneity of regression line slope

Dependent variables	Source of variations	F statistic	Sig. level
Self-control	Pretest*group	0.271	0.076
Mental health	Pretest*group	1.562	0.495
Mindfulness	Pretest*group	0.112	0.351

According to the results listed in Table 8, the significance level of the interaction effect of the group and the pretest is greater than 0.05; therefore, the assumption of homogeneity of the regression line for

the research variables is accepted. Since the assumption of homogeneity of the regression line slope is established, it becomes possible to use the analysis of variance test.

Table 9. Result of Mauchly's sphericity test for mental health dimensions

Variables	Mauchly's sphericity	Chi-square statistic	Sig. level
Physical symptoms	0.365	27.191	0.001
Anxiety symptoms	0.571	21.212	0.001
Social function	0.415	23.727	0.001
Depression	0.465	22.652	0.001

According to Table 9 regarding Mauchly's sphericity test, the significance level value for each of the mental health dimensions is 0.001; therefore, the assumption of sphericity is rejected. As a result, the assumption of the equality of the variances and, more precisely, the condition of homogeneity of the covariance matrix was not ensured, and there was a violation of the F statistical model. As a result, alternative tests, i.e. Greenhouse-Geisser conservative test, were used to investigate within-subject effects of the therapy, the results of which are shown in Table 10.

Table 10. Results of analysis of variance of repeated measurement for research variables in three stages of implementation

Variables	Variation sources	F statistic	Sig.	Effect coefficient	Statistical power
Physical symptoms	Group	24.720	0.001	0.371	0.999
	Time	5.611	0.007	0.211	0.833
	Interaction of time and group	6.380	0.001	0.371	0.908
Anxiety symptoms	Group	45.620	0.001	0.521	0.999
	Time	21.106	0.001	0.501	0.999
	Interaction of time and group	6.392	0.002	0.233	0.923

Social function	Group	26.392	0.001	0.598	0.999
	Time	9.809	0.001	0.318	0.976
	Interaction of time and group	9.200	0.001	0.305	0.978
Depression	Group	26.658	0.001	0.598	0.999
	Time	9.992	0.001	0.318	0.976
	Interaction of time and group	9.200	0.001	0.305	0.978

Results of Table 10 show that the intervention method by cognitive-behavioral couple therapy has caused a significant difference in the three stages of measurement in the scores of physical symptoms ($F=24.720$; $Sig=0.001$), anxiety symptoms ($F=45.620$; $Sig=0.001$), social function ($F=26.392$; $Sig=0.001$), and depression in the two groups, which means that the intervention method by cognitive-behavioral couple therapy has a significant effect on improving the mental health dimensions.

Result of Mauchly's sphericity test for self-control to prove the second hypothesis is given in Table 11:

Table 11.Result of Mauchly's sphericity test for self-control

Variables	Mauchly's sphericity	Chi-square statistic	Degree of freedom	Sig. level
Self-control	0.134	14.66	2	0.022

According to Table 11 regarding Mauchly's sphericity test, the significance level value for the variable of self-control is 0.001; therefore, the assumption of sphericity is rejected. As a result, the assumption of the equality of the variances and, more precisely, the condition of homogeneity of the covariance matrix was not ensured, and there was a violation of the F statistical model. As a result, alternative tests, i.e. Greenhouse-Geisser conservative test, were used to investigate within-subject effects of the therapy, the results of which are shown in Table 12.

Table 12. Results of variance analysis of repeated measurement for self-control in three stages of implementation

Variables	Variation sources	F statistic	Sig.	Effect coefficient	Statistical power
Self-control	Group	4.989	0.001	0.478	0.999
	Time	35.017	0.012	0.193	0.786
	Interaction of time and group	17.645	0.005	0.457	0.996

Results of Table 12 show that the intervention method by cognitive-behavioral couple therapy has caused a significant difference in the three stages of measurement in the scores of self-control (F=4.989; Sig=0.001) in the two groups, which means that the intervention method by cognitive-behavioral couple therapy has a significant effect on improving self-control.

Result of Mauchly's sphericity test for mindfulness to prove the third hypothesis is given in Table 13:

Table 13. Results of analysis of variance of repeated measurement for research variables in three stages of implementation

Variables	Mauchly's sphericity	Chi-square statistic	Degree of freedom
Mindfulness	0.169	15.22	0.034

According to Table 13 regarding Mauchly's sphericity test, the significance level value for the variable of mindfulness is 0.001; therefore, the assumption of sphericity is rejected. As a result, the assumption of the equality of the variances and, more precisely, the condition of homogeneity of the covariance matrix was not ensured, and there was a violation of the F statistical model. As a result, alternative tests, i.e. Greenhouse-Geisser conservative test, were used to investigate within-subject effects of the therapy, the results of which are shown in Table 12.

Table 14. Results of variance analysis of repeated measurement formindfulness in three stages ofimplementation

Variables	Variation sources	F statistic	Sig.	Effect coefficient	Statistical power
Mindfulness	Group	4.856	0.001	0.492	0.895
	Time	35.369	0.016	0.226	0.802
	Interaction of time and group	17.952	0.035	0.467	0.862

Results of Table 14 show that the intervention method by cognitive-behavioral couple therapy has caused a significant difference in the three stages of measurement in the scores of mindfulness (F=4.856; Sig=0.001)in the two groups, which means that the intervention method by cognitive-behavioral couple therapy has a significant effect on improving mindfulness.

Conclusion

Mental health in married women suffering from domestic violence participating in cognitive-behavioral couple therapy is different from the control group. The first finding of the present study showed that in the posttest stage, the intervention programs used, i.e. couple therapy using the cognitive-behavioral method, were effective in improving the mental health dimensions. Therefore, the first hypothesis of the present study is confirmed.Seddiqi (2019) in her research entitled evaluation of the effect of group cognitive behavioral therapy on the mental health of working women affected by domestic violence reached the conclusion that group cognitive behavioral therapy has an effect on improving mental health, decreasing anxiety and sleep disorders, improving social functioning, reducing depression and reducing physical symptoms of working women affected by domestic violence, which is consistent with the present finding.Angin et al. (2021) in research entitled applying cognitive-behavioral therapy to help survivors of dating violence: a pilot study has reached the conclusion that cognitive-behavioral therapy has had a significant effect on improving women's mental health dimensions, which is consistent with the present research. Lakin et al. (2021) in research entitled psychological interventions for survivors of intimate partner violence: an overview of the evidence and implementation

considerations have reached the conclusion that cognitive behavioral therapy has had a significant effect on improving women's mental health dimensions, which is consistent with the present research.

The explanation that can be given for this hypothesis is that the cognitive-behavioral couple therapy approach strives to create a balance in the couple's demands and then bring the couple's assessment of their demands closer together. If couples have a similar assessment of the resources and demands of their lives, it is considered as a strength in married life, which provides the basis for improving the quality of married life and, as a result, their mental health.

Self-control in married women suffering from domestic violence participating in cognitive-behavioral couple therapy is different from the control group. The first finding of the present study showed that in the posttest stage, the intervention program used, i.e. cognitive-behavioral couple therapy, was effective in improving self-control. Therefore, the second hypothesis of the present study is confirmed. Habigzang et al. (2018) in research entitled evaluation of the impact of a cognitive-behavioral intervention for women in domestic violence situations in Brazil have reached the conclusion that self-control in married women suffering from domestic violence participating in cognitive-behavioral couple therapy is different from the control group, which is consistent with the present research.

The explanation that can be given for this hypothesis is that the cognitive-behavioral couple therapy approach strives to create a balance in the couple's demands and then bring the couple's assessment of their demands closer together. It also leads to each couple being more resilient in their situation. This means that they become more sensitive to social situations and adjust their appearance according to the current situation, as a result, their self-control increases.

Also, mindfulness in married women suffering from domestic violence participating in cognitive-behavioral couple therapy is different from the control group. The first finding of the present study showed that in the posttest stage, the intervention program used, i.e. cognitive-behavioral couple therapy, was effective in improving mindfulness. Therefore, the third hypothesis of the present study is confirmed. Pitt et al. (2020) in research entitled implementation of a cognitive behavioral intervention on mindfulness for women who have experienced domestic violence and abuse have reached the conclusion that in the posttest stage, the used intervention program, i.e. couple therapy using cognitive-behavioral method, was effective in improving mindfulness, which is consistent with the present research.

The explanation that can be given for this hypothesis is that the cognitive-behavioral couple therapy approach strives to create a balance in the couple's demands and then bring the couple's assessment of their demands closer together. It also leads to each couple perceiving internal and external realities freely and without distortion, and having a great ability to face a wide range of thoughts, emotions and pleasant or unpleasant experiences, as a result, their mindfulness also increases.

It is recommended that the authorities of the health system pay special attention to violence against working women and hold meetings and conduct cognitive behavioral training in order to follow up and decrease it. It is also recommended to conduct a follow-up stage in future research. It is recommended to evaluate the effectiveness of couple therapy using the method of acceptance and commitment as well as cognitive behavioral therapy on other constructs in the field of marriage, including marital burnout, pursuing-distancing, and marital forgiveness, and to compare it with the results of other psychotherapies, especially Glasser's reality therapy and emotion-oriented approaches.

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